

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, thank you for taking your time to participate in this interview.

So my name is Anna Makarudze and I'm studying, I'm pursuing a Masters in Software Engineering Institute of Technology in Sweden. And I'm conducting a study on dependence management in open source projects. So my topic is vulnerabilities in OSS and FOSS dependencies and from a developer's perspective.

Speaker 2

Okay, yeah.

Speaker 1

So participation in this interview is voluntary and you can withdraw it in time.

It will stop the interview and you can skip any questions that you're not comfortable with answering and your response is will be anonymized. People will not be able to link you to your project. And then I'm recording this interview because I need to show evidence to my supervisors and my assessors that they actually took place.

Speaker 2

Okay, that seems reasonable.

Speaker 1

All right. So my topic is focused on how open source dependency is managed in projects with regards to supply chain attacks, because they're very common these days. But before we start, maybe you can introduce yourself and tell me with if you are active in open source, if you are a developer, contributor, or any of the projects. My focus is on five ecosystems, Python, the focus on the web framework, Django framework and then Java with a focus on Spring Boot, then Ruby with a focus on Ruby on Rails, and JavaScript Next.js, and then PHP with a focus on Laravel.

Speaker 1

So I'm looking on those five web frameworks and those five ecosystems. So you can tell me about yourself, how long you've contributed to the project that you're working on, or your experience as a developer as well, how long you've been in the software development industry, your job title and everything that will be useful.

Speaker 2

Okay, so I've been, not my name, is it? But I've been in the software development industry for 20 plus years now. I'm currently a CTO at a startup that we built on Django. I'm very involved in the Django web framework, not the other project, not the other ecosystems you've mentioned. I used to use PHP, but that was all a long time ago now.

So I'm on the Django Steering Council now. I was a former Django fellow. I was a Django fellow for five years, so working on the framework itself. And I was a member of the Django security team for eight years up until very recently. I stepped back for commitment purposes.

I also maintain a number of packages in the Django ecosystem and have done for many years, including Django rest framework, Django filter, crispy forms, Django compressor. So these are some of the more used projects in the space.

Does that answer the question?

Speaker 1

Yes, it does. So could you explain what your role in Django? You said you were a fellow in. Okay, so Django.

Speaker 2

I always described it as being like the janitors that keep the floor moving. But the idea was that they do the hard day-to-day stuff, which it's very hard to get done sustainably and reliably just on volunteer effort. Django, like many projects, is maintained on volunteer effort, but it's too big a project for that to just happen.

So Django, via the Django Software Foundation, contracts one or two or now are currently 3 fellows who work either full-time or part-time on a contract basis to do the day-to-day maintenance on the framework.

So one of the primary tasks there is handling triage and doing security releases and doing regular releases. But it's also pull request review and there's a community management aspect in terms of being involved in discussions.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. Okay. Could you explain, maybe you mentioned a number of teams in the Django framework. Maybe could you explain the governance structure of how those teams relate, especially to security issues in Django?

Speaker 2

Okay, so there's two main bodies which are the DSF board and they're responsible for the kind of, how shall I put it? corporate management of package. They look after the trademark, they do various things like run elections and whatnot, but they're not really involved in the technical governance of it.

And then there's the steering council, which helps to drive the technical direction.

And the main job there is trying to communicate, coordinate people from the community who've all got different opinions and try and facilitate the conversations and help drive those forward. Then the fellows, they do most of the day-to-day management.

And then there are teams to help. So there's an ops team that help keep the website up and running. There's various teams.

But the one that I served on that I think is relevant to what we're talking about today is the security team. And so Django has a security mailing list, which anybody can e-mail security at djangoproject.com. And then the members of the security team review the incoming reports and triage them to see if they are a security release and then coordinate with the fellows and the reporters to, in a secure and confidential way, put together a release.

And then that's announced maybe seven days before. It's like there will be a security release at this particular time on this particular day. And then the actual release is normally the fellow's responsibility to coordinate.

Speaker 1

Thank you. So are there any other ecosystems that your project relies on maybe using JavaScript dependencies apart from the Python ones or maybe other languages that you reply on?

Speaker 2

Okay, so we do in Django there is, there are some Javascript dependencies involved, particularly around the admin, where there has some Javascript involved there.

I do recall, where jQuery, for instance, we used jQuery for many years, where there'd be a need to update the jQuery version because of some security releasing in jQuery.

You said other than Python, but we coordinate very closely with the Python security team as well. And so quite often there's a discussion a report comes in, it seems realistic. And the question is, do we fix this in Django or is this a Python security issue?

And we have some back and forth with them. And we also work with the other web frameworks in the Python space, so Flask and Fast APIs. And we even coordinate with Ruby on the Ruby on Rails security team at times about, oh, do you know that there's this security patch problem in Django? It's likely that the same thing exists in Rails because the you know, the language is different, but the underlying implementation is is very similar. So we we try and coordinate across the ecosystems. Where we can.

Speaker 1

Okay, then, I wanted to know how much just are you as a developer of dangers that vulnerable dependence is present to your projects, not just Django. You mentioned a lot lots of other projects that you maintain in the open.

Speaker 2

Yeah, we are. How how aware are we of the the the threats that's. Yeah, I mean, so. Yeah, like, it's something that we take very seriously. So Django, I'll talk about Django briefly, but it's a philosophical thing throughout the whole ecosystem. But Django is very reluctant to take on a hard dependency. Like very, very often Django will build something internally rather than take on a third-party dependency.

Because there's a trust issue there. How secure is that? And how reliable is it? And a lot of projects don't have the kind of life cycle or stability guarantees that a project like Django has. Like an LTS version has multiple years where it needs to be supported. We can't just take on a new project that's popped up six months ago. And because who's to say it will still be around in six months' time, never mind about 3 years' time or five years' time.

So there's that. In my own projects, I'm very conscious of. I'm very, I'll try out a new project. If someone releases a project and I'll have a look at it, but to actually adopt it as a dependency that has to. It has to cross the threshold of trust, of confidence.

We have to have confidence in it. And without that, it's might be an interesting new project, but I'm not going to use it. You know, I might use it in a prototype, but not in a actual production. Scenario for quite a while.

Speaker 1

You raise an important issue about the trustworthiness. How do you get to decide that this project is trustworthy? I can use it.

Speaker 2

Okay. So one thing is, who's who's done it? If it's a if it's if it comes from a trust historically, trustworthy source, then that obviously is some points in its favor. You know, if there's a an established developer or established group of developers, if it's you know that that's a good thing.

Does it have a security policy, for instance, on on on the repo? Does it have contact? How would I reach out to the maintainer if there was a security report? Has the project been around for a while? Is it mature project? That's that. That's a question, a brand new project.

Well, where does it come from? What is its provenance? That's another thing. Does it have decent test coverage? You know, is it likely to, does it accept PRs from any, you know, are PRs accepted from anybody and are they merged perhaps too quickly?

You know, AI is a big issue at the moment, right? Lots and lots of pull requests are opened. Well, how are maintainers handling those? Are they just clicking Copilot review and Copilot reviews it and then they merge it? Well, that would be a red flag. That would be something to look out for. That would be a warning sign.

These kind of issues, I mean, there are databases as well of known vulnerabilities and there are scanners within each of the ecosystems that you can run tools that will say, hang on, is this project affected by this known vulnerability?

So to run those tools is an important thing to keep, you know. Normally, you put those as part of your ci flow. So you're like, hang on at least once a week. Are we running these kind of audit tools that tell us if there are new dependencies or new known vulnerabilities.

But there are 2 sides. There's the known ones, and then there's the the unknown ones and the unknown ones. All you can really do is look at these kind of sort of social metrics.

They're not there, but have a certain amount of ... How would I phrase it? Like, just be conservative about what you adopt. I think the risk is picking up too many dependencies

Would be my thought.

00:12:34 Speaker 1

Hmn. Then I also thank you for that. You already mentioned how to identify dependencies. I wanted to know how aware you are of supply chain attacks in their effects on projects if

you have encountered them or the risk that dependencies can give to your projects by using them.

00:12:55 Speaker 2

Yes. So I mean, there's some famous ones. What was the, I want to say XZ Utils. Was it XZ Utils that had the sort of long-term malicious contributor that it's okay. So once upon a time, you might have thought, well, you know, the worst that can happen is that somebody can just make a bad commit and we can revert the commit.

But with the scale of contributions, normally AI aided contributions. The scale of noise on a repo makes it harder and harder to have somebody who you trust in a position where they can visually audit every commit that goes through.

If there's only three commits since the last release, well, it's easy enough for somebody, for the releaser to look at it and check, okay, yeah, that one makes sense, that one makes sense, that one makes sense.

And so it's realistic that you can audit against those kind of supply chain attacks.

But if they're for your own repo, if you're if there's hundreds of commits since the last release, it's implausible that the releaser can go through every commit, every line that was changed and really verify that something hasn't stuck in.

And then so it becomes, well, okay, if I can't even do that process on my own repo, how can I trust that it was done on the repos that have come before? So it's a really big issue.

I don't think there's a golden, I haven't seen a golden solution to it yet, but yes, we're very aware, we're very conscious of it. re-emphasises the need to be very cautious about what dependencies you adopt and what their processes are and

You know, things like trusted publishers for PyPI is a nice thing where previously people would release from CI, from GitHub Action, say they'd have these long-lived tokens that, or who's to say that that token didn't leak in months and months?

GitHub now have this trusted with PyPI, they have this trusted publishers thing where the token is only, it's only very short lived thing. So it's very unlikely that it leaked and could then be hijacked to push a bad release.

There's a technical term for it that escapes me momentarily, but where they've pushed a release which wasn't authorized. So those are the kind of considerations that come to mind when you raise that question.

00:15:45 Speaker 1

I also want to ask what influences you to update to to influence the decision to update to new versions of the dependencies within your projects, because some of the supply chain attacks the append when people do an update to a dependence that they already had.

00:16:07 Speaker 2

Yeah. So normally, in an ideal world, a new version would be released and you'd be able to update straight away. So there's this notion at the moment that people are talking about of the cool down period where you allow, you know, perhaps the new releases come down and you don't update straight away because quite often if there is a problem in a version, it will be caught.

And this happened with the XZ, right it was it was got made its way into the main branch of the distributions but it was caught in the testing phase before they were finally released to people before everyone updated so in the end that wasn't too bad but if you release if you automatically update your dependencies the second a new version is released and then you push that straight to production without any decent testing or any decent like window to see if there are any problems that have been introduced that can that can be.

A concern with something like Django, there's only a release every eight months, so it takes, it would take a long, there's a long window between when, potentially when an update is for a dependency is released and then when the next version of Django, which will be going out to users, is. Again, I don't know exactly what the best practices are meant to be here.

You know, so we've got this idea of a cooldown, okay, so we won't update, give it seven days, but if everybody doesn't update seven days, then how is the, you need somebody to proactively look at the update before your cooldown window has expired.

So it's, you know, there's a cat and mouse game there.

Speaker 1

So one of the things, one of the major problems in open source is people start projects, maintain them for a bit and then for some reason life opens and they leave the project. I want to know how do you normally check the maintenance of your dependencies in your projects? You know, you talked about trust, so maybe the person who developed it at the first you trusted them, but then They left the project and then it over to other people.

Speaker 2

Yeah, you just have to be on your, be aware of these things. So I mean, how did I end up maintaining all these projects in the Django ecosystem? Well, I was building my business around them. And then Django Filter I was using became unmaintained.

And I needed that to work. So I took on Django Filter. And the same with Crispy Forms. I took on Crispy Forms. And then compressor that I was using needed working.

So I just ended up adopting these projects because they were exactly in this position of being unmaintained. How do you trust the new maintainer? Well, they have to earn that trust again. So you have to be conscious that it's not a one time decision.

It's a it's something is this dependency still trustworthy? If not, do I have capacity to work on it myself? Or is it likely that it's going to get picked up by somebody else? If that's somebody else, who is it?

So within the Django community, they had the Jazz Band Project and they've now got Django Commons, which is similar to Jazz Bands, winding up because of the problem with AI spam. It used to be that anybody could join and very much it was a kind of trust environment where, well, what's the worst thing happened?

Someone made bad, you know, they make a mistake and we can patch it up before the next release. But you can't trust that now. And it can't be the case that anybody with an LLM can just go and merge any pull request they want.

And so I think this is an interesting topic now in that not just from the, you know, not just from the security point, but from the security point combined with the big increase in volume that we see in open source activity because the tooling has made it so much easier to contribute.

Speaker 1

Okay, so.

Speaker 2

Does that answer your question?

Speaker 1

Yes, it does.

Speaker 2

Okay.

Speaker 1

Okay, so suppose one of your dependencies you have, there's been a public site CVE. Normally, how long does it take for you to then update that vulnerable dependent in your project?

Speaker 2

Well, not long, because we have these alerts that come through saying, you know, so there are tools which we'll monitor for the known Cves, and then they'll open an issue saying, Hey, you've got a security. You know, a number of your projects are affected by, you know, X security thing, and you can.

You can look. So it's not always the case that you have to update immediately, because it might be that your project isn't using the the affected code in the way that the security the security issue requires.

So sometimes you can, it's not as pressing as others, but and there's two, there's two thoughts there. One is for an actual production project, you have to update basically in, you know, straight away, you know, modulo checking you know, I'm not affected by this.

Okay, well, in that case, it's not, it's not pressing on, but if you are affected, you basically update immediately. Then there's the ecosystem packages where they might have a dependency on a vulnerable version, but unless you've got a pin in place, so you say, oh, exactly that version, normally it doesn't affect end users because they can just update the affected package and you're your package will work with the newer version automatically without you having to manually do a new release because the dependency was affected.

The only time that's not the case is if you've got a pin, if you say no, below version 11, say, and it's version 10.9 that was affected and version 11 with the fix, well, then you have to change your pin because otherwise you're saying to users, you must use an affected version.

And so it's another reason not to put top pins on your project. So you say, look, I support at least, I need you to use at least version seven. That's fine. A minimum version is fine, but don't put in a maximum version because who's to say what comes out?

And normally if users just, they run pip upgrade with the eager dependency updates, it'll just pull in the latest versions that are compatible. And as long as you've, as long as you haven't top pinned, from a maintainer's perspective, as long as you haven't put a top in in, normally, the security release, the security vulnerability in one of your dependencies doesn't affect you, not directly.

Doesn't create you extra work. Normally. No, I mean, sometimes, oh, you know, I'm directly using the affected API in the affected way. Yeah, you have to change the way you use. You use your code, you know because potentially that that the fix, the security fix can break your package in theory. and that that, you know, over the long run that happens short, but that doesn't happen very often.

Speaker 1

All right. Okay. Okay. So one thing that I've noticed with you said you use javascript packages sometimes. Yeah, a lot of deprecated packages on Npm.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

00:24:01 Speaker 1

And how do you address that when one of your

00:24:04 Speaker 1

package becomes deprecated. I know you already maintained Django packages, but now JavaScript is in another ecosystem. The package that is deprecated in this. Is one of your dependencies, how do you handle that?

Speaker 2

Good question. It's difficult. I mean, I have to admit to finding the JavaScript world quite confusing. So my main strategy there is to minimize my, you know, my exposure to JavaScript. So one reason why I like packages like say HTMX and Alpine JS is that they're single script and they're kind of self-contained and there's no massive build step and there's no massive dependency tree with so many packages down the graph that I don't, I can't possibly audit all of those.

And it was if I do, if I do the same application using, say, a full framework like React, then I'll have this big dependency tree that as somebody from the Python world, it's impossible for me to be familiar enough with every single package in that tree to audit those properly.

I mean, you know, there are specialist JavaScript developers who struggle with that in their own in their own projects. So how am I as a Python developer who uses JavaScript, how am I supposed to be able to do something which is a struggle for people who specialize in that world? The answer is I can't.

So I need to have a different strategy. And small, I would very much favor packages which don't have a big dependency tree, which is self-contained, which I can bend a particular

version into my own application. So I'm not depending on NPX you know, Npm install every time I deploy these kind of things. It's not ideal. It's not foolproof, certainly, but it's probably the best that's realistically attainable for me. Always looking at new techniques, but.

Speaker 1

You mentioned tooling for audit auditing. Yeah. Could you probably provide a few examples of those tools that you use.

Speaker 2

Oh yeah, I mean as well. Hang on. I think what was the somebody who did it?

There was a really great blog post just this week from the guy who maintains talks and pip debt tree and things like that, he gave a full a full breakdown of the Python developer's guide to security. And so think tools are pip will pip freeze can generate hashes for the packages.

And then when you go to install, it can check that the hash is matched. That's one thing.

There's a pip audit tool which will, you know, go through and check the list of dependencies against the CVE database to see if there are dependencies.

These are these kind of things. And there was much more advanced things in his post, which I need to work on. I need to find you the link. I might have to do it after the call and send it to you.

But the new kids on the block are these software bill of materials and all of these tools, which are more sophisticated, more advanced, but it's not clear to me yet that they how they easily fit into the workflow, some of these more advanced options.

And each one, I think, is a defense in depth measure. It's not that individually, any one of them is sufficient. But if you run all of these tools together, then you've got a kind of safety net that if it gets past one, well, it might be caught here.

And the combination of these practices is what makes them secure because any given one, might fail um I would let me look after the call and I will send you the link to that to that particular post but that's but so that's you know somebody who's very involved in packaging and in testing and in distribution and their take on what the best practices are as of you know March 2026 when we're doing this call.

Speaker 1

Thank you I really appreciate that. Okay, then have any of the projects that you worked on ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

No, I don't think so. Dependencies have had security issues, absolutely. But that's not a supply chain attack per se. That's the fact that every project has security. You know, everybody has issues. I cannot think of an example where, you know, one of the, you know, the direct dependency levels where a malicious code was introduced or a malicious version of the package was deployed. Yeah, as an attack vector. No.

Speaker 1

You mentioned a lot of tools and practices that you can use to at least try and avoid supply chain attacks. Yeah. Do you, are there any challenges that you face in regards to addressing vulnerable dependencies within projects?

Speaker 2

Yeah, the issues come where a project is undermaintained. So if a, for whatever reason, developers have moved on, life gets in the way. If a project is undermaintained, then it, yeah, it can be an issue to get a dependent, security fix in and released in a timely manner because people just don't have the capacity.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you. And then do you have any recommendations for other developers or software development teams on how they can either mitigate supply chain attacks within their projects, especially due to dependency trees or maybe some practice that they can implement in their projects as well towards that?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I mean, I think I think it's just a not just. It's a question of following the best practices and trying to follow the best practice. And so you know. I've just, you know don't give out commit bit. Don't just let anybody randomly merge commits to your project and then release them. Do the due diligence.

If you're going to maintain a project, then you have to at least, if you're putting your name on it, you're saying, I've done this. You have to at least have looked at the code that's going in. You know, you need to have thought through the risks of some contributor that you don't know, not acting in best faith.

Beyond that, the tooling that tells you when there's a vulnerability in one of your updates, those are, that's great. Then update it, you know, then actually do the updates.

Yeah, just follow the, follow the guides. There are guides. Be conscious and then be diligent.

Speaker 1

Oh, thank you. I think that that was all from me.

Speaker 2

Yeah, okay.

Speaker 1

I don't know if you have anything else to say feedback for me.

Speaker 2

So no, I mean, like, you know, that's the topic. So yeah, I mean. I guess there's a the the thought that I have the lingering thought I have is that there's the same. It's got a different levels of risk exposure here. It's different threat models. If you're just a

You know, if you're doing a small personal project, you know, with a few dependencies that, you know, very well known, that's sort of core ones like Django itself, you're probably fine.

If you're a corporate entity and you're deploying a high risk, you know, a high risk project that's worth somebody trying to attack, then you're going to have a different threat model and you're going to take these things more more seriously.

They're going to be more, it's going to be more important that you've demonstrated that you've taken the right approaches.

And I think my only kind of thought is for in the small project, it's not necessarily the case that you need to do all the same things that you do in the much more significant one because it's just not appropriate that you take those steps.

I don't know. I mean, you know, we'll try and do what we can.

Speaker 1

Thank you.

Speaker 1

I just wanted to one the package that you mentioned.

00:33:45 Speaker 1

XZ. XZ Yeah, it was.

Speaker 1

Yes. Yeah, it's one of the. I quoted that documentation, so.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you.

Speaker 1

No, problem.

Speaker 2

No problem.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much for your time. I'll stop recording now. I hope that was recording.

Oh, yeah. Anyway.